

СЎЗ САЊАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

6 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 6, НОМЕР 3

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 6, ISSUE 3

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА | INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

№3 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9297-2023-3>

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ISSN: 2181-9297

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

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SPEECH ACT THEORY AND ITS CLASSIFICATIONS

 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8249734>

ANNOTATION

The significance of this article is that, here is given theory of speech acts and their classifications by different scholars, it also distinguishes the elements of speech acts in utterances. There some implications about the compliments as a sub group of speech acts and which category they belong to. This thesis highlights the importance of studying speech acts when learning English for mastering linguistic reality and obtaining communicative competence by speakers, and it examines the role and function of speech act from the perspective of scholars.

Key words: speech acts, pragmatics, taxonomy, classification, facets, elements, compliments.

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ТЕОРИЯ РЕЧЕВОГО АКТА И ЕЕ КЛАССИФИКАЦИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Значение данной статьи в том, что здесь дана теория речевых актов и их классификации разными учеными, выделены элементы речевых актов в высказываниях. Есть некоторые предположения о комплиментах как о подгруппе речевых актов и о том, к какой категории они относятся. В этой диссертации подчеркивается важность изучения речевых актов при изучении английского языка для овладения языковой реальностью и приобретения коммуникативной компетенции говорящими, а также рассматриваются роль и функции речевого акта с точки зрения ученых.

Ключевые слова: речевые акты, прагматика, таксономия, классификация, грани, элементы, комплименты.

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NUTQ AKTI NAZARIYASI VA UNING TASNIFLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolaning ahamiyati shundan iboratki, unda nutqiy harakatlar nazariyasi va ularning turli olimlar tomonidan tasnifi berilgan, gaplarda nutqiy harakat elementlari yoritilgan. Nutq harakatlarining bir qismi sifatida maqtovlar va ular qaysi toifaga tegishliligi haqida ba'zi taxminlar mavjud. Ushbu dissertatsiya lingvistik voqelikni o'zlashtirish va so'zlovchilar tomonidan kommunikativ kompetentsiyani egallash uchun ingliz tilini o'rganishda nutq aktlarini o'rganish muhimligini ta'kidlaydi, shuningdek, nutq aktining roli va funksiyalarini olimlar nuqtai nazaridan ko'rib chiqadi.

Kalit so'zlar: nutqiy harakatlar, pragmatika, taksonomiya, tasnif, qirralar, elementlar, maqtovlar.

Introduction

Around the turn of the 20th century, researchers compared speech to language as a potential system of signs designed for storing and transmitting information, focusing primarily on questions related to the generation of speech, or the replication of linguistic units during communication. Speech was perceived as a wholly separate word creation with a clear communicative and stylistic orientation due to the variety of human activity (scientific-theoretical, daily, poetic).

Scientists from the Oxford School (J. Austin, J. Searle, and G.P. Grice) focused on the study of common human language in its context during the 1960s and 1970s. These scholars contend that the fundamental goal of natural language is to promote interpersonal communication. As a result, the focus of linguistic research has shifted to the individual with his or her personal communication goals as well as the elements of the communicative context that help those goals be effectively attained. According to the Oxford school, the objective world comes into play as a factor that creates a communication situation and determines the speaker's goals and objectives first and foremost. As a result, pragmatic linguistics, sometimes referred to as pragmalinguistics or pragmatics (from the Greek pragma, "business", genus pad. - pragmatos), developed as a new field of linguistic study. The data that had previously been the purview of other sciences, such as encyclopedic, sociological, and psychological data, piqued the curiosity of linguists. Of course, the achievements of formal and content linguistics in the past have not lost their significance; rather, they have merged into the idea of a broader approach to language.

Methods

The research framework for communicative activity now includes a wide range of extralinguistic factors in addition to linguistic means of expression, such as the linguistic proficiency of the participants in the speech act, their interaction in the communication process, the environment in which this communication is carried out, the target settings of the subject and addressee of the speech, speech etiquette, and specific features of the use of language me. As a result, there are currently no set boundaries for the study of acceptable pragmatics.

The term "pragmatics" is very broad and covers a wide range of topics, such as the relationship between the participants in communication, the environment in which communication occurs, the use of stylistic and emotive language, and the personalities of the speaker and listener during the production and delivery of speech. Since sociolinguistics, psycholinguistics, and other linguistic specialties are concerned with how language functions in society, pragmatics is therefore viewed as the linguistics of speech in a broad sense. Pragmatics provides the response to the query, "What do you wish to communicate with this word?" The theory of speech acts, which is founded on the notion that speaking begins before language, was created as a result.

Ludwig Wittgenstein's thoughts on language games served as the earliest foreshadowing or prediction of the concepts of Speech act theory. The core ideas of J.L. Austin's late 1930s-developed Speech act theory were presented in his 1952–1954 Oxford lectures.

In order to clarify utterances, Austin (1962) differentiates three components (facets) of a speech act:

1) The locutionary act - the act of saying something; the act of expressing a phrase only for the purpose of producing a meaningful linguistic statement.

2) the illocutionary act — what you're doing when you talk; an act done by a speaker by uttering certain words, such as commanding, promising, or threatening.

3) the perlocutionary act - the impact of what you say; an act of speaking or writing that has an action as its goal but does not accomplish or constitute the action in and of itself, such as persuading or convincing.

Results

Can speech acts be classified, and if so, how? J. Austin singles out the following speech acts:

Exercitives (acts of exercising power) for example: I order, advise, encourage, etc.

Verdicts or "judgmental acts" containing a judgment about something, for example: I think, evaluate, believe, etc.

Commissions (acts of obligation) for example: I undertake, I promise, I give my word, etc.

Behabitives (formulas of social etiquette, usually expressing a reaction to the behavior of other people) for example: congratulations, I apologize, I take my words back, etc.

Expositives (acts-explanations) for example: I answer, object, agree, etc.

All of these categories of speech actions, on the other hand, were of a general character and did not provide for the selection of some specific speech acts.

In the general theory of speech actions and their typologies, compliments are either not represented at all or are combined with other speech acts.

As was already said, J. Austin's category of behabitives comprise social conduct rules and etiquette statements such excuses, expressions of sympathy, compliments, and congratulations. According to J. Austin, behaviors include the concept of a reaction to other people's behavior as well as an attitude about someone's previous or upcoming behavior and an express proclamation of that attitude.

In J. Austin's proposed taxonomy of distinct speech actions, "compliment" is not included. The speech actions we are looking at might, however, be linked to the group of behabitives because the praise highlights the polite nature of the speech act performed in etiquette communication. Contrarily, a complement may incorporate an evaluative element in its semantic structure or serve as a token of admiration or respect before veering off into judgements, which are sometimes described as "the execution of a value judgment."

J. Searle, a disciple of J. Austin, draws on his predecessor's theories. He differentiated the illocutionary and propositional components of a speech and offered a more unified taxonomy of illocutionary acts:

representative or assertive - statements expressing the speaker's belief in the truth of his propositional content;

directives - statements in which the speaker tries to persuade the listeners to take some action;

commissives - statements in which the speaker assumes certain obligations regarding the subsequent course of events;

expressives - statements denoting the speaker's mental state in relation to something;

declarations - statements, the use of which the speaker tries to persuade the listeners to perform.

This classification places the compliment that we're considering within the heading of expressives. Expressive remarks are comments that reveal the speaker's emotions, thoughts, and—most importantly—attitude about the actions, behaviors, and events of other people. The speaker pronounces this statement with varying degrees of passion. The main elements that govern the illocutionary chain of a group of expressives are the needs of sincerity in relation to the state of events (situation) and their propositional content.

The major argument advanced by D. Vanderveken (1990) in the monograph "Speech Acts" is that illocutionary acts serve as the primary units of meaning in the use and comprehension of language. The typology of J. Searle matches D. Vanderveken's theory of illocutionary actions. D. Vanderveken is the first to expressly put the verb complimenter in the list of verbs comprising a class of expressives, in contrast to J. Austin and J. Searle.

According to him, expressive illocutionary verbs are called illocutionary forces, the purpose of which is the expression of the mental states of the speaker. It is, first of all, joy, approval or dissatisfaction.

For example:

I express my regrets to you about this. Alternatively, I express my gratitude to you (gratitude). In addition to verbal means of expressing mental states, the communicant may resort to the use of non-verbal means of expression. For example, joy can be expressed with a smile, laughter.

Consider the classification of speech acts by D. Wunderlich (1977), where the researcher differentiated speech acts according to their functions:

representatives: approval, statement, reports, descriptions, explanations, assurances;

directives: promptings, requests, orders, instructions, orders, instructions, normative acts;

commissions: promises, announcements, threats;

declarations: names, definitions, appointments, sentences, setting the agenda, opening the meeting;

erotatives: questions;

satisfactions: apologies, gratitude, justifications, excuses;

retractives: statement about the ability to fulfill a promise, clarification about a previously made statement, permission;

vocatives: appeal, call

This typology of communicative-intentional types of statements largely coincides with the classification of J. Searle. Here, complimentary statements find their place in the group of satisfactions.

Discussion

The five categories of speech acts are described in further detail below.

Representatives are speaking acts that tie the speaker to the truth of the conveyed proposition and, as a result, have truth-value (also known as assertives or constatives in Austin's original performative/constative dualism). They express the speaker's point of view. Examples of paradigm occurrences are asserting, claiming, concluding, reporting, and speaking. An illustration might be, "Paris is the capital of France."

"Last night, I watched a fantastic documentary."

Speech activities known as **directives** aim to encourage the listener to follow the speaker's instructions. They express the speaker's call for the recipient to act. Examples of paradigm instances are counsel, instructions, orders, questions, and requests. For illustration, say, "Pass me the salt, please."

"Don't drink that," I said.

Commissives are verbal acts that commit the speaker to a certain future behavior. They convey the speaker's motivation to act. Examples of paradigm circumstances are offers, oaths, pledges, promises, denials, and threats. Using the example above, "I'll see you at 6 tomorrow"

"I do!"

Expressives are verbal behaviors that reveal the psychological state or emotion of the speaker, such as happiness, sorrow, or loves and dislikes.

Examples of paradigm instances are apologizing, blaming, clapping, praising, and thanking. Using an example, say, "I'm so sorry about yesterday."

"Thank you so much for helping me."

Declaratory acts, often known as declaratives, are verbal actions that immediately alter the state of affairs. They are referred to as "institutionalized performatives" since their effective execution depends on complex extralinguistic processes. By performing this type of speech act, the speaker effects changes in reality; that is, he or she establishes a connection between the propositional content and the outside world. Examples of paradigm circumstances are bidding in bridge, declaring war, excluding someone from a group, firing someone from a job, and nominating a candidate. Using the example above, "I now declare you husband and wife."

"You are fired!"

Conclusion

Some of these new classifications are formulated in formal/grammatical terms, others in semantic/pragmatic terms, and still others on the basis of the combined formal/grammatical and semantic/pragmatic modes. Among all of these classifications, Searle's typology of speech acts remains the most influential. This is because it rests upon a clear and rich conceptual framework.

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